

Poverty in Nigeria: The Political Economy Perspective

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Abstract:

The paper aims at analyzing the widespread poverty level in Nigeria within the ambit of political economy. Secondary sources of data were used. The startling poverty rate in Nigeria over the years is said to be a direct consequence of our forefathers' ill activities which trend is still hunting the system till date. The paper suggests that poverty is rooted in leadership style and that since political actions set the pace for economic empowerment, leaders use political power to drive more by personal vagary than of economic realities to the benefit of all. The method of critical analysis was used. Quite a reasonable number of Nigerians do not benefit from governance, hence poverty has been very high in both rural and urban centers and predominantly so with perverse groups. The major cause of poverty in Nigeria is leadership and reasons for their behavior were seen to be poor governance, bond to self-challenge, political power as business enterprise, god-fatherism, religious problem, ethnic problem, corruption, illiteracy problem, poor legislative function, limited diversification of the economy, poor practice of rule of law, poverty of ideas, constitutional weakness. It is recommended that for poverty to be alleviated in the country, political and economic structures which allow corruption to go unfettered should be strengthened.

Keywords: Corruption, Poverty, Governance, Political Economy, Dialectic materialism.

1.0 Introduction

Perpetuation of our fathers' activities trends the society and without historical perspectives, trends in society cannot be corrected if lessons are not learnt from past mistakes except that their activities brought better antecedents. Political economy as a discipline can be said to be the study of the role of historical and economic processes in shaping the society (Dobb, 1964). It has come to be closely associated with key concepts developed by Marx in his analysis of dialectic materialism. Dialectic materialism gives primacy to material or economic conditions of a society. The thrust being on how the understanding of a society's politics and culture depends primarily on the understanding of its economic structure as defined by the relations between employers of labour and the working class in the process of production (Akpuru-Aja, 1998). In Marx's approach of the concepts, he focused on class processes or relationships that centered more profoundly on the economic determinism of orthodox human behaviour. Thus, political economy makes extensive and intensive use of class analysis in

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establishing how conducts frame the society and history, but does so in the context of political, social, environmental and cultural processes as well as in economic perspectives.

Dobb (1964) however stressed that on the priority of production and chiefly on social relations of production (containing appropriation or proprietorship of the resources of production), political economy essentially align the historical angle approach. In this perspective, the emergent “bourgeois” (or capitalist) society sets the distinctive focus and emphasis on social relations. To be more precise therefore, political economy concerns itself specifically with understanding the role of capitalist exploitation (as the prevalence of a specific class arrangement or set of class processes) in the understanding of society and history. Until its post-structuralist views came about to provide an alternative to orthodox (*neoclassical*) economic theory as propagated by Marx and others through a more economic determinist versions, economic ideology had been dominated by capitalist socio-economic formation which accentuated itself on survival of the fittest syndrome than on establishing strong promise to help in correcting the ills of economic domination and perpetuity of oppression or to fundamentally understand how humans can use the past trends in society and historical perspectives to assess the present circumstances and to some extent, anticipate the future.

In essence, political economy can help locate the root causes of third world underdevelopment and poverty either on issues of imperialism, colonialism and neo-colonialism on the one hand and also from the internal contradictions peculiar to the third world countries as fundamental causes of their underdevelopment and penury. To this end, the subject matter is a sure way to provide the working class and all working people with knowledge of the laws governing the economic development of society and makes them to fulfill successfully the task facing them. Even when it may highlight to the working people the reasons for their enslavement, poverty and deprivations, it can also be used to help the oppressed and exploited to understand their reality and ways out of their contradictions. Specifically, therefore, it enables the oppressed and the impoverished especially of the working class not to depend on the arbitrary will of capitalists’ tendencies which propagate self-actualisation and survival of the fittest syndrome.

Ibietan & Oghatar (2013) notes that successive governments in Nigeria have not seem to indicate any desire to transform the economy to the benefit of all and sundry and hence, inequality gap keeps widening and poverty remains paradoxical as the incidence keep rising in the midst of plenty and rising periods of economic growth (Omoyibo, 2013). Nigeria is endowed with both human and natural resources and has had an increasing national income; yet, a larger section of her population languishes in poverty (Iyoboyi, 2012, Aigbokhan, 1998; Alesina & Perotti, 1996). Bhalla & Lapeyre (2016) relate it to the concept of social exclusion and leadership issue as an emerging phenomenon especially in developing countries. Poverty has multiplier effects and linkages such that it affects societal life in different perspectives including life expectancy, security, education and relationships. Efforts to eradicate it had been intensified globally through reforms, interventions and sustainable development goals to improve living standards. Nations are now categorised on the scale of development based on indices that have direct bearing on poverty, unemployment and inequality. Hence, poverty is listed as a risk factor in coping with societal values and in assessing quality of life (Pearson, 2015).

Be it in terms of provision of infrastructure, human capacity development and even in the realm of social, environmental and political development, Nigeria seem not to have any ardent or clear cut policy direction. The country had experimented some of these reformative ideals

with several development plans and other forms of interventions from pre-independence era but since it was not a core mandate, the needed transformation has continued to elude the citizenry in spite of the revenue generation the country have had over the years from crude oil sales alone. Hunger, high crime rate, wide spread poverty, social and spatial inequalities, rural-urban migration, inadequate healthcare services, lack of access to education, amongst others have taken their toll on the people.

It could be that difficulties arise in translating plans and policies into effective poverty reduction interventions even as successive governments may not have intended to eradicate poverty as propagated. This issue is more pertinent now as the government if sincere, are finding it challenging to programme and budget through sectors/channels which resources would maximize welfare gains in public expenditure management.

The economy has grown from million to billion naira and now trillion naira on the expenditure side of the budget. It would therefore, not be surprising if the people are having higher levels of standard of living. Better still, if there are infrastructures to improve commerce within the system or social amenities to raise the welfare of average citizen of the economy. All these are not there, yet we always have a very high estimated expenditure. This indicates that something is definitely wrong either with the way government budgets its expenditure profile or there is outright misappropriation or in the ways and manners it has always been computed or applied or that there has been constant misplaced priority in the policy objectives of government. Government may however, have insincerity of purpose in eradicating poverty. These realities, which constitute a departure from theoretical ground, bring up reason for this study to attempt to unveil reasons for observed departure.

There are very few countries in the world that are so endowed as Nigeria. In the 1960s, Nigeria, Malaysia, Indonesia, Taiwan, Singapore and South Korea had similar incomes per capita, GDP growth rates, and under-developed political structures. Today, the “Asian Tigers” (as the south-east Asian countries are popularly known) have escaped under-development and poverty partly because of the way in which their economies have been managed”. Ekpo (2003) acknowledges that “the Nigerian economy has experienced all the phases of a typical business cycle: decline, depression or recession, recovery, and boom” and that “none of the booms ... has resulted in any significant restructuring or transformation of the economy.” This had culminated into the country’s lingering economic crises of over six decades, characterized by stagnation and sluggish, if not negative growth, concurrence of unemployment and inflation, industrial under-capacity utilization, deterioration of socio-economic and production-support infrastructure, fiscal and external payments deficits, chronic exchange rate instability, skyrocketing poverty incidence and high level of inequality etc.

Given all the various policy measures so far taken by the Nigerian government, the incidence of poverty in Nigeria is still very high. The poverty analysis report for Nigeria released by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2016) shows that the average poverty incidence for Nigeria is 73% with Sokoto and Niger States having incidence as high as 83% and 75% respectively. It could therefore be seen that though growth has improved, it has not reflected on poverty level, unemployment and inequality gap as these issues continues to be widespread and pervasive (Obi, 2007). The government had aimed at attaining the millennium development goal of reducing poverty by half by end of 2015 but could not achieve it. Nigeria has a comparatively high population in Africa and it is recorded that on the average 45-50 percent of sub-Saharan Africans live below the poverty line indicating that a high percentage of Nigerians live below the line. In fact, about 63 percent of Nigerians according to the World

Bank, 2006 and CBN, 2011 reports were living below the poverty line of N305 a year in 1985 prices. Nigeria's substantial resource endowments underscore the country's enormous potentials and the country is said to be a paradox (World Bank, 1996). Paradox, because the poverty level contradicts her immense wealth. Particularly worrisome is that the country earned over USD400 billion from just one resource: petroleum, during the last three decades of the twentieth century. Rather than remarkable progress in national socio-economic development, Nigeria retrogressed to become one of the 20 poorest countries at the threshold of twenty-first century whereas she was among the richest 50 in the early 1970s. The gross domestic product (GDP) which was \$86 billion in 2016 is twice less than that for 1981 translating into per capita income decline from about \$1150 in 1981 to about \$300 in 2001, \$120 in 2012 and about \$60 in 2018. The per capita income is below half of the sub-Saharan African average and the country has the third highest number of poor people in the world.

2.0 Review of Relevant Literature

Government exists to execute certain functions and bring up policies in the common interest of all. The key task is to protect and promote the welfare of its citizens although given some circumstances, the role of government differs especially between developed and developing countries (Bose, Haque, & Osborn, 2007). In doing this, the government must choose the approach that tries to maximize benefits accrued. It should be recalled that due to the successes of active Keynesian government and the Marshall Plan in the 1940s, the government had been regarded as a prime mover in correcting all problems obstructing economic performance. To provide man's basic needs, man interacts with the other aspects of the society. The economic activity of man forms the basis for his social relations in the society. The mode of production comprises the productivity forces and the social relations of production. Productive forces comprise men, the objects of product and the instruments of labour when associated in the production process. The people's relation in the production process are influenced by the character of the ownership of the means of production, their role in the production process, the position they occupy, the exchange activities among them, as well as the distribution pattern of their output. The main features of the social realities are the motion and dynamism impelled by contradictions innate in its related and complex elements, including the struggle among the social classes. The material foundation of a nation therefore determines the character of her superstructure, including social-political, bureaucracy, religion, and the gamut of the social systems, which are mere expressions of the contradictions among social classes that are in constant struggle in the product process.

World Bank (1993) comprehends that it is how power is exercised that brings about the main feature of the social system in the management of a country's political, economic and social resources for development. The emphasis here, according to the World Bank, is 'the use of power to control political and economic resources of the nation'. Thus government functionality is about securing political power in order to control economic power for the purpose of nation's development. Put differently, it is about using nation's wealth for the benefit of the nation. The questions arising therefrom are: who constitutes the nation and is it really true in all cases? If not, why and if so, why so much deprivation in some environments especially of African ascendancy? As expected, a nation comprises of all the residents both citizens and foreigners but how then would the benefits are only in few hands? It may have been so in some other countries before they attended the 'developed' status but they had fast tracked their economic management ideals to ensure poverty, inequality and unemployment are moderate. If the nation is about every citizen, then why is there so much oppression in developing countries? Would we say the economic managers are not conscious of this idea?

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Dudley Seer (1997) inspired questions on what constitutes well-being in a given society which were:

“The questions to ask about a country’s development are therefore: What has been happening to poverty? What has been happening to unemployment? What has been happening to inequality? If all three of these have declined from high levels, then beyond doubt this has been a period of development for the country concerned. If one or two of these problems have been growing worse, especially if all three have, it would be strange to call the result ‘development’, even if per capita income had doubled” (Todaro and Smith, 2011).

Controlling power should be of benefit to improve welfare but if not achieved, what’s the essence of the control? Whereas IMF (2016) sees governance as ‘all aspects of the way a country is governed, its economic policies and regulatory framework’. From here, governance has to do with the totality of governmental actions and activities that are geared or directed toward making and realizing effective economic policies. The definition lays emphasis on ‘economic policies’ which is regarded as the backbone of the nation’s stability and development. Suffice to say a well-planned economic policy is a precondition for the survival, stability and development of the nation.

The concept in relation to the governed has for long been an issue around in political discourse depicting the tasks of carrying on governmental activities or assignment (in Governance Barometer: <http://www.gdrc.org/u-gov/governance-understand.html>) on the people’s welfare. While the definition is true to the developed nations of the world, it is far from being true in the third world countries, especially in most African nations.

Good Governance has been variously defined often to suit different purposes. It is through good governance that impact of governmental activities can be felt, particularly in the area of economic growth and development. The governance pattern in developing nations has rather impoverished large number of their citizens. Poverty deals ruthlessly with majority of people. The outstanding revelation from Nigeria’s Vice-President Yemi Osinbajo that about 110 million Nigerians (61%) are still living below poverty line testifies to the fact that poverty is really ravaging the nation while the masses appears helpless (Osibanjo, 2015).

It should however be noted that a precise definition of poverty is not a guarantee of a more effective policy response. Policies that sometimes are direct and focused have been noted to have problems but however diverse and descriptive these definitions are; they are quite useful in explaining the conditions of poverty where numbers cannot. Gurr (1970) sees it as “a perceived discrepancy between man’s value expectation and value capabilities.” To him, ‘value expectation’ means the goods and conditions of life people think they are rightly entitled while ‘value capabilities’ refer to “the goods and conditions of life they think they are capable of attaining or maintaining given the social means available to them.” Gurr’s theory explains that people compare the conditions of life to which they could attain to the economic reality they find themselves and also consider opportunities that are abound given the resources endowment within their environment.

Nevertheless, the dependency theory that was developed in the late 1950s have that economic growth in the advanced industrialized countries rather truncate growth in poorer countries. The theory suggests that economic activity/advice from richer countries often led to serious

economic problems in the poorer countries. The neoclassical theory had assumed that economic growth was beneficial to all (Pareto optimal) even if the benefits were not always equally shared. Explanation to the theory conclude that poor countries only export primary commodities to the rich countries that would then convert those commodities to manufactured products and sold them back to the poorer countries at exorbitant prices. The "Value Added" by manufacturing a usable product always cost more than the primary products used to create those products. Therefore, poorer countries would never be earning enough from their export earnings to pay for their imports. Prebisch's solution was similarly straightforward: poorer countries should embark on programs of import substitution so that they need not purchase the manufactured products from the richer countries. The poorer countries can still sell primary products in the world market, but should not use their foreign exchange reserves to purchase manufactures from abroad.

Three issues made this policy difficult to follow. The first is that the internal markets of the poorer countries were not large enough to support the economies of scale used by the richer countries to keep their prices low. The second issue concerned the political will of the poorer countries as to whether a transformation from being primary products producers was possible or desirable. The final issue revolved around the extent to which the poorer countries actually had control of their primary products, particularly in the area of selling those products abroad. These obstacles to the import substitution policy led others to think a little more creatively and historically at the relationship between rich and poor countries.

At this point dependency theory was viewed as a possible way of explaining the persistent poverty of the poorer countries. The traditional neoclassical approach said virtually nothing on this question except to assert that the poorer countries were late in coming to solid economic practices and that as soon as they learned the techniques of modern economics, then the poverty would begin to subside. However, Marxists theorists viewed the persistent poverty as a consequence of capitalist exploitation. And a new body of thought, called the world systems approach, argued that the poverty was a direct consequence of the evolution of the international political economy into a fairly rigid division of labor which favored the rich and penalized the poor.

The false-paradigm model posits that underdevelopment is due to faulty and inappropriate advice provided by well-meaning but often uninformed, biased and ethnocentric international (often western) expert advisers to developing countries. Here, IMF and World Banks took a lot of blame from the advocators of this model.

2.2 Extant Leadership Character in the Underdevelopment Status and Poverty in Nigeria

Poor Governance: Arisi and Ukadike (2011) posit that human beings were born with the prospect to make live better in their communities through the mechanism of good governance but these could only be achieved in a well-run system. The system to which favourable interdependence are harped on growth, poverty reduction and sustainable development; as well as respect for the rule of law, human rights, peace and security among others. On the contrary, a major challenge to quest for Nigeria's greatness is leadership. Nigeria's search for the most cultured and best informed minds with integrity and wisdom of both men and women that could take the nation to the peak level of addressing these peculiar ideals have remained elusive. According to Conable (1997) is the degree to which governance delivers on the promise of human rights; civil, cultural, economic, political and social rights that count.

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Nwoye (2005) argues that the essence of governance is fundamentally about touching peoples' lives positively. To do this requires creating a broad consensus platform that will integrate and empower the people to be effective partners in the process of social alteration. Amundsen (2010) claims that Nigeria is heavily affected by 'resource curse' as the country has experienced a population of more impoverished people now than what it was 50 years ago and poor economic development performance despite huge revenues from oil. Nwagboso and Duke (2012) contend that Ghana and South Africa were colonized like Nigeria but they seem to fare better in development. Currently Nigeria is faced with myriads of problems prominent among which are poverty, corruption, kidnapping, insecurity, unemployment, infrastructural decay, ethno-religious crises and many more. These problems though were issues few years ago in these two countries but had been surmounted to barest minimum due to better management of the economy. Thus, Nigerian leadership style has been a threat and clog in her wheel of progress towards achievement of economic growth and stable polity.

Bond to Self-Challenge: To Achebe (1984), the Nigerian problem is the unwillingness or inability of the leadership to bond to self-challenge themselves in character which can be said to be the hallmark of true leadership. Instead, many indulge in amassing public property to become personal and hence govern as if the jurisdiction is their personal businesses. Institutions of governance are subsumed and are answerable to them while the people now become servants. Whereas social and other amenities abound in where the political leaders reside such as the government reserved areas (GRA's), and other choice areas set only for the wealthy and political class like Banana Island, Victoria Island, Ikoyi, Lekki Beach areas in Lagos state, Maitama, Asokoro villa among others in Abuja. Social amenities are concentrated in all these reserved areas to the detriment of other places populated by ordinary Nigerian citizens. Besides social amenities are the heavy presence of state apparatuses in governance to ensure their safety and security. Accordingly, Achebe has twice turned down the award of national honour offer of the title of 'Commander of the Order of the Federal Republic' in 2004 from Nigeria's then President Olusegun Obasanjo and again in 2011 from President Goodluck Jonathan. To him, "What's the good of being a democracy if people are hungry and despondent and the infrastructures are not there," He told the British Broadcasting Corporation in 2004, explaining his decision. "There is no security of life. Parts of the country are alienated. Religious conflicts spring up now and again. The country is not working."

Political power as Business Enterprise: Annan, former Secretary-General of United Nations (UN) argues that political leaders have contributed to the underdevelopment nature of their various states by the pattern of governance they offered for their countries. According to him, "power gets personalized in the winner takes-all kind of politics...there are insufficient accountability of leaders, lack of transparency in regimes, inadequate checks and balances, non-adherence to the rule of law...and excessive political control" (Annan, 2012 cited in Mbah, 2013). Adegami and Uche (2016) assert also that: the political leaders in Nigeria could best be described as political merchants to affirm Annan's viewpoint. To them, the political class sees politics as a business enterprise that should bring forth huge profits. They do not believe in service to the people; instead they are self-serving as they serve themselves more than the governed, hence always play politics of wealth acquisition. Many came to power to amass wealth. This thus becomes the bane of Nigeria's efforts at development. Obo, Coker and Omenka, (2014), adds that service delivery cannot be said to be the political class mindset but of self-interest. Agagu and Ola (2011) calls them "harbingers of the scourge of poverty and crisis".

God Fatherism: Nwigwe (2003) contends that Nigeria's governance style could qualify as a government infested with power drunken, self-seeking, ideology-barren, orientation-less operatives; usually selected by their kind and of course scarcely ever elected by the people. He referred to such government as “mafia government” being that elected or appointed public officer no longer owns responsibility to the people but to the political god father. Much of the national and state funds are used in settling them to the detriment of the masses. The resultant effect has remained abysmal performance of these officers (Alozie in Onuoha and Ezeribe, 2012).

Religious problem: This has taken a great toll on the underdevelopment nature and poverty situation in the country. The incessant bomb attacks by the Boko Haram Islamic Sect which is escalating every day would not create room for any meaningful economic activities. Despite the bill passed on anti-terrorism by the Nigerian National Assembly on February 17th, 2011 and the effort of past governments to negotiate with the Islamic sect, the anticipated cease fire has remained elusive. Consequently, not only is the prospects of good governance undermined and worsened by the Boko Haram insurgency, the problem constitutes a major threat to development and Nigeria’s status of a nation state. This happens because most of the leaders are of the same religious affiliation hence would not react to their atrocities.

Ethnicity Problem: This is a bane in the wheels of progress in the country. Before any person is appointed into any political office, one of the first considerations is the ethnicity. Nnoli (1980) posits that ethnicity effect could be said to be more devastating on Nigeria politics than religion. There is no more room for efficiency and effectiveness and that was the reason the principle of federal character was introduced as a policy directive. Onimisi (2012), posits that the quest for relevance by many ethnic groups has given rise to mutual distrust and disharmony. The North and South dichotomy is a push for ethnic domination in governance and an evidence of ethno-centrism and a vote of no hope in Nigeria ‘nationhood’. Consequently, people are more ethnic inclined hence loyalty to ethnicity than nationhood. Everyone is after what could be taken out of her than imputed into her as a nation. In such clime, patriotism is to self-interest only. None is obliged to maintain or secure public infrastructure and none keeps faith with another except of same ethnic nationality. Thus, public officials breach public trust and official oath at will and cared less of what happens to people not of same ethnic clime. A nationless condition lacks patriotism to sustain common values, create and maintain commonwealth hence, adopts ad hoc method or solution to lingering problems. Citizenship is therefore meaningless and it becomes the proverbial ‘to your tent alone’ thus, poverty in other ethnic groups is of no consequence.

Corruption and Greed: Another disturbing and damaging factor is the level of corruption and greed. It is unprecedented. This has made extremely wealthy military and political leaders. Nigeria ranked 130th position out of 180 countries surveyed by Transparency International (2014). The effects of corruption in Nigeria have been ample. The underdevelopment status in lack of basic infrastructures, misuse of both human and natural resources, mediocrity in professional and leadership positions, defective leadership outputs, fuel scarcity in an oil producing nation, falling standards of education and work output, high unemployment rates, the ever-widening gap between the rich and poor to mention just a few are consequences from it. The multiplier effect has been the mass spread of poverty and our unenviable position in the list of poor and underdeveloped countries amidst rich natural resources. Similarly, electoral corruption is prevalent. Votes are purchased, promise of political office or special favors, coercion, intimidation, and interference with freedom of election, killing and maiming of people in the electoral process and a situation where losers end up as the winners are cases

of corruption (Adeyemi, 2012). Corruption impedes economic development, the growth of democratic institutions, and the ability of developing countries to plan appropriately.

Illiteracy Problem: There is also educational dimension to poverty in Nigeria. Poverty is concentrated among persons with no education and those with only primary education (NBS, 2011). It implies that the less educated the head, the more likely that the household would be poor. Employers which are mainly fronts to political office holders insist of recruiting fresh graduates below 25 years. The labour policy places the children of the poor at a disadvantage from that of the rich who ordinarily enjoy uninterrupted education. It is common knowledge that children of affluent homes have easy access to gainful employment as their parents provide the needed links. Children from poor background are left in the dark in pursuit of a decent job.

Poor Legislative Function: The members of parliament are about the highest income earners in the country even with no evident contribution to national development. Most are mainly after their sitting allowance and whatever spoils are presented within the chamber. Thus, they hardly are thoughtful of bringing up legislative matters that bother on poor peoples' plight. On the oversight functions, they most often adopt careless attitude about the Executives activities maybe because all of them are pursuing the same goal of amassing.

Limited Diversification of the Economy: The emergence of 'the black gold' (oil) has further enabled the underdevelopment status of the country and hence poverty situation as the people now see cheap funds from the exploration and cared less to diversify the economy. The emergence of oil wealth has widened the income gap in Nigeria as those who have access to political power have the link to engage in oil business. The oil business is often used as a means of political settlement in Nigeria. For resource-rich countries like Nigeria, the process is exacerbated by the three processes often associated with 'resource curse', namely: The Dutch disease, macroeconomic volatility, and deteriorating governance.

Poor Practice of Rule of Law: There is a trait among us Nigerian leaders which is the penchant for ignoring rules of law except of recent that some of them hearken to it. The political office holder believes that the law is only meant for the poor to obey hence the proverbial "sacred cow" syndrome becomes a bane and consequently, the leaders can do and undo and the law would not catch up with them. In a fact, the constitution has even protected the executives from being sued not minding the heinous crime committed by them.

Poverty of Ideas: Most of the political office holders cannot boast of any agenda or action plan to execute before being brought into office. Some are of stupid slogans like "I am the best. Vote for me". A sensible person will ask whether that could represent the manifesto. A lot are brought in just to settle them for some favour done without thinking whether such person have the wherewithal to service delivery. Whether they perform in office or not does not matter and no queries after all. How would they think of germane ideas that would propel growth and development to enhance living standard?

The Constitutional Weakness: The 1999 constitution adopted was prepared and effected by the military and hence could be said to be ineffective in capturing most of the ills exhibited. It over empowered the executives and gives them leverage to detect and despite years of agitation for the adoption of 2013 constitutional conference, the political class refuses to implement as the present one emboldens them with authority. Those seeking political offices have to be endorsed first by the executives and they are called "the anointed ones" and

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whether the win or not, everything will be done to manipulate the process in their favour. Institutions and other agencies of governance are only being instructed and sometimes bypassed. The qualification to even the presidency becomes an apology to the country.

Culture: Daniel Etounga Manguelle wrote a piece titled “Does Africa Need a Cultural Adjustment?” Culture matters in every society. The culture promotes servitude hence, where elders are, the young should not be involved. Young peoples’ ideas are seemingly disregarded as they are portrayed to be of no value. In some cases, servants are castrated so that they will not be tempted to have affairs with any of their masters’ family members. Some expect servants to worship them as gods. Most Africans cum Nigerians work to live but does not live to work. An average Nigerian citizen has high propensity to feast hence our societies are structured around pleasure. Everything is a pretext for celebration: birth, death, baptism, marriage, birthday, promotion, election, return from a short or a long trip, mourning, opening or closure of Congress, traditional and religious feasts. Whether one’s salary is considerable or modest, whether one’s granaries are empty or full, the feast must be beautiful and must include the maximum possible number of guests and ensure that every guest gets satisfaction in every form of consumables. Nevertheless, the society believe so much in witch doctor and our leaders surround themselves with host of them and nothing that really matters in politics without recourse to consulting witchcrafts. Occult counselors, responsible for assuring that authorities keep their power by detecting and neutralizing possible opponents, have powers that makes them more influential. All these attributes only promote poverty as monies that could have utilized in providing essentialities are spent frivolously.

3.0 The Political Economy Perspective to Poverty

Over the years, intellectual curiosity has emerged on issues like the inevitability or otherwise of class struggles. Class struggle entails the conflict of opposing forces represented by differing material status and interests (Ake, 2003). According to Marx, the most outstanding cause is the existence of private property and the tendency on the part of the property class to treat the property-less class as non-existent. Similarly, competing explanations have emerged on the causes of African cum Nigerian poverty and backwardness especially of the role of leadership in governance and foreign allies in its perpetuation. Nigeria is about her 60th year of independence and she is yet to take an opportunity for a comprehensive stocktaking and assessment of its economic and political performance over the years. The overall verdict is not quite cheering. Nigeria has not performed as much as its peers at independence, which include Malaysia, Brazil and India. Some smaller countries including Ghana, Rwanda and Botswana are rated to be faring better in quite a number of socio-economic and political indices. That the majority of Nigerians are disillusioned and despondent is not state secret. The state of the economy in the midst of huge government revenues is a sharp contrast to the level of poverty, unemployment and inequality evident in the country. People bemoan the manifest “growth without development” being experienced, even as the ruling class and their collaborators in the private sector continued to revel in assessed opulence. Indeed, high economic growth rate has been brandished over the years, but the reverse is the reality in terms of indicators of development, as manifest challenges in governance continued to compromise otherwise good intentions of budgetary provisions.

Poverty, unemployment and inequality have been on the rise. Youth Unemployment/Underemployment rate stood at 42.24 % as at the first quarter of 2016 (National Bureau of Statistics, 2016) while within the same period, the GINI coefficient index. It is difficult for an economy to excel in a society where there is total collapse of

values, which should form the very foundation of a normal society. It is also difficult for the citizens to have access to basic needs of life in a society with weak institutions. The Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) March 2019 report and other institutional reports (NBS, 2016, SERAP, 2019) shows that, poverty incidence is as high as 73% with highest incidence in the North East and North West and death toll on disease infected people due to hunger is increasing. The country is said to be in such a bad situation that more lives would be lost if relieve or some form of assistance does not come soon. The question arising from all these bad economic, social and political performance is: does this have to do majorly to the influence of the developed countries and their comprador allies? In giving explanation to it, the utmost vulnerability of the people may be unconnected with such euphemism and of the different Classical development theories and paradigms except those that bordered on the dualism paradigms.

International dependence revolution propagates that the dependence and dominance relationship between the rich and poor nations could possibly be the reason Africa cum Nigeria is underdeveloped and poor. The dependence theory attributes the existence and continuance underdevelopment primarily to the historical evolution of a highly unequal international capitalist system of rich-poor country relationships. That the rich nations are intentionally exploitative and unintentionally neglectful and because of unequal power relationship, any attempt by the poor countries to be self-reliant and independent becomes difficult and sometimes impossible. Whereas, false paradigm accentuates the deceit and ill advice of international institutions to which African countries adopt wholeheartedly. In all these, there could be some reasonable level of the West influence on the outcomes of the situation in our environment but it could also be reasoned that African underdevelopment is neither of the whites nor the direct bearing of these classical development theories but the blacks themselves. After all, some of these advices were given to other countries and yet, they considered the direct implications first to the citizenry and on the general economic prosperity before decision would be taken on whether to adopt the advice or not. Why would the economic managers be careless to implement their advice wholly without filtering the odds? While we complain of the Bretton Wood institutions and other foreign allies in the bad economic performance of the country, we quite often seek solution from these institutions and their allies.

At present, the Nigerian government is seeking economic assistance in all forms of activities from the Western nations whereas the general mindset of the people including the leaders is that the Western countries and their allies are our problem. The questions again are: why seek help in their territory? Won't they cause more havoc or perpetuate more economic woes? With this syndrome, the Nigerian policy managers can only be compared to a black hole. Thus, no matter how much assistance they may receive, they can hardly expect it to have any effect in the emancipation of the people since the leadership is not ready to exhibit appropriate and functional progress in economic sphere. We should note that the Western nations are after their interests and nothing will stop them from achieving it as there is no sentiment in international politics and economic matters that bother on welfare and progress. Would African cum Nigerian leaders assume that any advice given will be without their interests? It would be foolhardy. It could therefore be claimed that some of the black elite groups (landlords, military rulers, merchants, entrepreneurs, higher level public officials, etc.) who enjoy high incomes, social status and political power with their selfish-interest perpetuate this syndrome to which they were rewarded. So poverty and underdevelopment of African cum Nigerian economy which is attributed to the existence and policies of the industrial capitalist

countries and their extensions of comprador groups in less developed countries which makes poverty be seen as externally induced can be taken to be a farce.

Our forefathers (local elites and leaders) ill activities and behavioural antecedents actualized the prevalence of high poverty incidence level in the country and the trend is dominating our thinking and cultural viewpoint till date. The value system has corrupted the ineptness in our reasoning that averagely, the intrinsic value of our heritage lies on desiring to reap where we had not sown otherwise the average African cum Nigerian leader could be said to be occasioned by poverty of ideas. The basic tenet that has evolved our cultural and economic apocalypse has been the desire to amass and in that course victimize, maim and possibly kill without conscience and value for another's existence than the pursuit of general improvement in standard of living and other economics/technological ideals. It should be noted that, a great portion of the historical analysis of slavery was perpetrated by the locals (the blacks). The British Empire colonized India, and some other far-east countries yet the depth and magnitude of slavery in those countries were not comparable to the level it was in Africa. In analyzing the characteristics of past events, we need to ask questions and in this regard the questions are: 'why was there so much slavery in Africa?', 'why was the black man taken into slavery?', 'who took the white men into the hinterlands of Africa for slavery to be perpetuated?' 'who were those selling their kinsmen to the whites?'. The single answer to this plunge is that, the deeds were planned, effected and executed by the black men. They sold their black brothers to the white merchants. One could not blame the white merchants as they were opportunists.

The Classicist economic system propagates the pursuit of self-interest and in the process, wherever the opportunity arises, they take advantage of. Capitalist tendencies had enveloped the market structural subjugation and sub-consciously the operators will explore and exploit. The Colonialist came into Africa to look for opportunities to create more wealth for themselves and in the process take back or repatriate any meaningful ideals that would be of economic benefit to them at home for their social progress and well-being. Our children, brothers and sisters also travel out to search for greener pastures. In reaching Africa, they saw opportunity in getting human labour at almost zero cost. Slavery had already been instituted as the culture of the people through the traditional institutions and other activity forms and all that they did was to commercialize what they saw in African environment. Six decades after the independence of many African countries, the system of governance has not changed for anything better but has even grown worse than during the colonial era. The political leaders are perpetuating slavery on their people even the more. They keep them in perpetual penury and lack and hence in servitude permanently. They are ready to enslave to any capacity apart from their immediate family members and political ally. To them, if these people are taken out from poverty, who will serve them? Who will do the errands and political thuggery? Otherwise, there is no reason the poverty profile should geometrically be rising given the amount of oil production and revenue earned from it alone in a country like Nigeria.

The more than \$400 billion earned from oil production alone since independence is meaningless to an average Nigerian condition and hence are indifferent to possible outcomes on it or what happens in the sector. The leaders had taken advantage of the system against the principle of equity, justice and fairness. The reason even till date, the country is being seen as one of the poorest country in the world. What is experienced at all levels of government is failure on the part of leadership. For instance, citizens provide themselves security (high fenced walls, night watchmen, vigilantes, window and doors protectors, etc.), water (borehole and water wells or buy from water retailers), power (generators, solar and other means), roads

(at least to where they live while repairing impassable ones), health facilities (the patient buys all essentialities needed for treatment and pays privately for ambulance service, no drugs and essential facilities for diagnosing but the leaders budget billions for their healthcare attainment abroad), education (private schools which the political leaders or allies own thrive at all levels and people pay enormously for the services as government schools at all levels are not functional and at tertiary level, Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) has been on their throat for facilities and funding to be improved). Yet, the same leaders are boasting that they have done tremendously for the citizens and should therefore be applauded and that citizens have no right to ask questions. If all these monies used in funding all these services privately were saved, would it not have helped in peoples' plight and credit made available to enhance living standards? Some questions arising from here are: 'Is it the colonialists that are handling the affairs of the country even as it has been declared as one of the poorest countries in the world?', 'what was the country's poverty level before, during and after the colonial era?' There is a peculiar nature of the Africans that beats imagination which has to be dealt with. How would the so-called political leaders go on senseless looting spree? An individual could boast of being richer than a state without showing evidence of the source of wealth.

Overnight looting of billions and trillions without a trace of the richness yet they will come with their deceitful 'war against corruption' as propagated by the present civilian regime in Nigeria. Some of the loots are even in foreign currencies stored in foreign banks to which are being loaned to the country and interest paid on the money to the foreign banks. Some of the leaders had even died with the monies still being kept there without a trace which could eventually be confiscated by the banks. Cry my beloved country is a literature textbook by Alan Paton in the 1970s. It pictured a country's behavioural pattern based on antecedents and lessons were expected to be learnt therefrom yet at the twilight of the 21st Century, some countries are still in dungeon of economic management. Have we ever experienced or heard in any country where monies are hidden in septic tanks or buried underground or stacked in overhead water tanks? That could only be found in Nigeria because they are stolen and would never want them traced. Yet the society is in penury and the leaders will not stop their gluttonous looting of the wealth of the people. This is in spite of the bogus and jumbo pay political office holders are earning.

In the recent COVID-19 lock down period and given the need for stocking of food stuff to cater for the family within the period, the federal government of Nigeria blatantly refused to pay lecturers' salary in the name of not registering with Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS). Even in the most recent 2022 ASUU struck, the government has also refused to pay lecturers' salaries for good eight months. Can the world imagine the insensitivity of the Nigerian leaders? The questions arising therefrom could be that where did these political leaders expect the lecturers to get funds to stock food for the family? After now, do they expect same level of dedication to work? The government only adjudged the lecturers to be good for nothing and therefore could all die without any regret whereas the world sees them as the bedrock of value and of knowledge. The government of Nigeria signed their death warrant and dead people do not rise from the grave to teach. That's the type of government Nigeria has. Jhingan (2003) defines poverty as misery-go-round plaguing the less developed countries. Truly, misery went round lecturers' homes because if when salaries were paid and most were complaining, what then happens as the peanut (as some claim) were not paid?

Gosztonyi *et al.* (2009) observed that despite Nigeria's size, and the energy and talents of her people, she has failed to achieve her full potentials because of poor leadership, poor infrastructure and a history of high levels of corruption. They noted that the Nigerian market had long been notorious for graft, partly as a result of the country's reputation as the world leader in financial crime, as well as the systematic abuse of the oil wealth over several decades by the political class. Consequently, they argued, many leading investors that might otherwise flocked the country stayed away. As far back as the 1970s, there was this advert that Andrew is checking out from the country. Could this not be attributed to the way the economy had been and is still being managed till now?

In 2000, a Swiss banking commission's report indicted the Swiss Banks for failure to follow compliance process in allowing family and friends of the Abacha access to accounts and deposits amounting to \$600 million US dollars. The same year, a total of more than \$1 billion US dollars were found in various accounts through Europe (Wikipedia). The 2006 study of corruption by the Transparency International and Geottingen University ranked Nigeria as the most corrupt nation among 54 countries listed in the study with Parkistan as the second highest (More, 2007) similarly, the Transparency International corrupt index (CPI) of 85 countries in 2015 ranked Nigeria 81 (Lipset and Lenz, 2017) worse still, the 2018 corruption perception Index (CPI) saw Nigeria further down, as she ranked 90 out of 91 countries pooled, and second position as the most corrupt country, with Bangladesh coming first. Generally, Nigeria is seen as one of the most corrupt countries in the world, and this poses a great challenge to her public administration.

The state rather carries campaign of calumny and terror with the connivance and, sometimes, financial backing of the foreign ally companies against the people. Shell Petroleum and Development Company (SPDC) some years ago purchased arms to the Nigerian police guarding its installations. The Nigerian government accepted the olive branch extended because it was an opportunity to maim. MTN provided the legislature with phone lines and unquantified account balance just to ensure that they would not query their charges on the people. It was received with thanks. If the leaders had stood against such acts, how could they manifest? Over the years, the Nigerian federal government and the foreign allied companies have perpetuated penury on the populace. The varied oil spills in the Niger Delta have deprived greater percentage of people their livelihood and yet no compensation were paid and when the people would fight for it to be paid, the leaders would see it as opportunity to steal the funds to enrich themselves the more. Programs to quell the discontentment of the people of Niger Delta keep being illusionised. Even under the military regimes of Generals Ibrahim Babangida (1985-1993) and Abacha (1993-1998), the Oil Mineral Producing Areas Development Commission (OMPADEC) coordinated development projects in the area. But like most institutions, OMPADEC turned out to be a cesspool, in which billions of dollars disappeared into the private pockets of commission operators and soldiers. The oil companies, on their part, would set up several projects like provision of basic infrastructure, scholarship schemes, and community-relations units through which community members could express their needs but would later have cold feet in effecting the projects and would even deny responsibility for any ecological destruction.

It is not surprising to an average Nigerian that in the federal government revised budget for 2020, they intended to cut the budget for health and education sectors by N50 billion and N100 billion respectively to use in the fight against corona virus pandemic this April 2020 if not for Socio-Economic Rights and Accountability Project (SERAP) that had been leaning their stringent voices to good governance and hence had constantly been engaging

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government on legislative activism and public accountability issues and other concerned individuals that intervened and appealed that the two sectors were the ones that affects the common citizen directly and advised that there were other overheads that could have been used without necessarily affecting the masses.

In 2007/2008 when the world experienced economic and financial crisis and most banks were in trouble, the government brought out N3trillion to bail out the banks. First, they gave the banks N239 billion, another N620 billion and N1.725 trillion making a total of N3 trillion because the banks were owned by the people within the leadership cadre and their cohorts and these were supposedly non-refundable bail out. So it was for the aviation sector with a whooping N500 billion and even NOLLYWOOD were bailed out with billions of Naira. These are private sector organisations and yet government provided the necessary bail-out funds. The universities in the country only needed N1.3 trillion to fix infrastructures and other urgent needs, the government cried wolves because the World Bank told them that Africans do not need higher education, and that they only need middle-level technical education.

There are copious outcomes of perpetuation of evil on the people. The Odi village genocide during Obasanjo regime in 1999, the 2011 Ikeja cantonment ammunition explosion with thousands of death which the then president vented on media personnel “on whether he was supposed to be there”, the January 1, 2018 killings of Benue indigenes by the Miyetti Allah group to which they openly accepted responsibilities and yet nothing happened to them. A good number of Nigerians suffer untold dehumanization and sometimes death in the course of seeking latitude from domestic hardship and sufferings to countries that are not as endowed as Nigeria, yet those countries become a much more favoured country to escape to, after all, our lives would be much better according to some of them. There are examples of how the resentment of the Niger Delta citizens transformed an environmental issue into a struggle for resource control and finally into militancy, kidnapping, bunkering, etc. We are witnessing the radicalisation of North-Eastern Nigeria into religious intolerance and political brinkmanship. These threats to national security are probably the symptoms of long years of mass structural poverty in a society where hopelessness and despair are gradually displacing optimism and confidence.

4.0 The Way Forward

Most government economic policies since the mid-1960s had been flawed with that which drove poverty and unemployment to high levels. The import-substitution policy coaxed the industrial system to be import-dependent as the system neglected the use of local content in production hence, employment of nationals in industrial settings could not be effected. It was therefore not poverty reducing policy. Efforts at diversifying the economy has not borne any much fruit as the country rather depends on revenue from oil production and there often had been oil price boom which fixated the system to the sector the more and therefore indigenous roots were lacking manpower deployment and hence most people could not be gainfully employed in meaningful productive venture. Nevertheless, at the macroeconomics level, fiscal deficit had most often been on the rise since 1970s which generated high inflation rate and consequently, both the domestic and external balance was a problem. The government macro-economic (fiscal and monetary) policies would adopt contractions to mop the excess liquidity

which had rather exacerbated and dipped the medium to long term credit availability to the real sector of the economy. Thus, the small and medium scale enterprises were restricted to operate only within certain limits and hence, massive employment of both human and natural resources could not be which would have boosted economic activities.

Aside this however, the financial sector had not been at the forefront of enhancing investments by their refusal to grant medium and long term loans to the real sector as they rather prefer the short term loans granting to boost their profit margins. Start-ups were even the most affected as the banks were scared of accumulating bad debts as they were never certain of the success of these lines of investment. The IMF and World Bank prescribed structural adjustment programme that was adopted in 1986 brought about policies that made nations cut down social expenditure to be able to repay their loans. It shortened funds which was vital for economic growth and development. In the light of this, Nigerians were tied up on development funds as credit was restricted hence induced poverty. Much as the policy helped improve macro-economic perspective, the welfare of the people was confined. The country was also tied to opening up its economy and being primarily commodity exporters, it led to worsening terms of trade with the advanced countries of the world and hence welfare was abridged. One other implication of the structural adjustment programme in Nigeria was incessant hikes in the price of petroleum products, which negatively impacted industrial productivity and real incomes, resulting in a general deterioration of living standards. Worst scenarios were recorded between 1999 and 2007, when fuel hikes were the norm rather than the exception, and where flimsy than rational reasons were advanced.

As a general economic policy towards the improvement of welfare, various governments at all levels and at different times embarked on programmes amongst which included the Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), Better Life Programme (BLP), Family Support Programme (FSP), National Directorate of Employment (NDE), People's Bank of Nigeria, Family Economic Advancement Programme (FEAP), Federal Urban Mass Transit Program, National Agency for Mass Literacy and National Agricultural Land Development Authority (NALDA), Agricultural Development Programmes (ADP), Nomadic and Adult Education Programme (NAEP) and National Poverty Eradication Programme' (NAPEP). According to Ekpo (2003), these programmes could not create the apparent impact on poverty level because they were not tied to the real sector of the economy. Government through its macroeconomic policies should therefore be able to set appropriate targets and priorities to be much more functional in achieving the expected outcomes especially as they relate to well-being of communities (especially the poor), as well as stimulating investment and employment creation.

It is generally agreed that the responsibility for insuring the delivery of critical services (basic necessities of life such as food, clothing, light and shelter among others) lies with the government and the provision must be achieved at high levels of efficiency and effectiveness yet successive governments finds it difficult to provide them especially power infrastructure that drives other sectors. Poverty reduction and improving human welfare should overshadow the essence of governance and hence the government must have a think tank that would generate functional ideas to ensure that a lot of essential and necessary infrastructures are established to propel economic activities and elevate mental reasoning above parochialism.

In the whole 774 LGAs and FCT, we cannot boast of a single well-articulated storage facility for farm produce. Knowing too well that most of the poor live in the rural area and that most often, their farm produce has a lot of wastages, the government could as a matter of urgency

establish storage facilities to reduce wastage of perishable goods and where possible buy-off these items from them just to encourage their efforts.

The formation of co-operative society has been seen as one great effort in funding initiatives but yet the society has been infiltrated with corrupt managers. The formation of these societies will help elevate great chunk of youths to establish cottage industries which if managed properly can be groomed into a formidable business concern.

The provision of irrigational facilities to ensure production of adequate and sustained food supply should be a priority. Farmers that cannot provide themselves with the facility will be very much encouraged.

Power infrastructure is the bedrock of most businesses. The government should ensure that the supply is near constant and at affordable rate especially to those small and medium scale enterprises against individual generation of any kind which would be too expensive to compete with products from where the supply is constant and the rate being affordable.

The reform of the public service should imbibe reorientation and re-engineering of government apparatuses. This must emphasize the drive for efficiency and effectiveness and of the rule of law applicable to all and sundry. It should also seek to build institutional capacity so as to improve performance in public management.

5.0 Conclusion

The prospects for breaking Africa's cum Nigeria's poverty cycle seems less promising when viewed from the prism of the status quo (Umo, 2009). The way and manner of our leadership has so far failed to connect the essential elements and conditions that could assure success through the short term to the long term. African leaders were at independence, expected especially those who had been marginalized by colonialism, to engage all sections of society in a national discourse on state reconstruction and provide effective governance structures and resource allocation systems that guaranteed people the right to freely engage in economic activities. Instead of doing such, most of them rather undertook primarily opportunistic reforms that expressively increased their political power and heightened their ability to control the stream of legislation and the allocation of resources (Levine, 2009). Emerging from these reform efforts were highly oppressive, exploitative and intrusive states, quite like those that existed in the continent before and during the colonial period. The post-independence period saw bureaucratic corruption and rent seeking as the leaders and public office holders fortified obstinate economic policies in an effort to coax the economy to their own advantage. The citizenry especially vulnerable groups--women, children, rural inhabitants, and the unemployed and underemployed youths were severely impoverished and marginalized.

As reported in Umo, 2009, Lord Keynes insightfully observed over 70 years ago that the difficulty lies not in new ideas but in escaping from the old ideas. This means that the problem lies mainly in delinking from the old ideas which have continually promoted poverty incidence in order to embrace more promising options. Besides, the extant ways are not in consonance with contemporary historical experience countries which have overcome absolute poverty. The ruling elite in Nigeria must be sure of what they want. They must take a step back and change direction. To be more focused and in order to realize the transcending national and social prejudices and conflicts, the first consideration is for the leadership to see

everyone as important and relevant in the cause of nation building and make the country's growth and development the basis for every policy initiative. Let it be conceived that economic growth and development could be seen as being deductive. Deductive, in that, we take the teachings, the essence and the attributes of research hypothesis and approve that a correct theory can be derived only when all of the natural and social phenomena are found to fall in line with the conclusions derived from that hypothesis. This hypothetical method has been proven to be very fruitful in the economic development of the advanced countries by taking humans as being relevant in the cause of development.

Nigeria maybe an independent country but cannot be said to be independent or in isolation in relation to international community. Every aspect of the country must become sensitive to political ideals that encourages than discourages, imbibe the experiences from other developed nations, correct past mistakes and have value for life. Except otherwise we want to continue to be backward and dependent, leadership with human face must be a virtue. The era of institutionalizing governance as family affairs or with allies must give way to reality of governance with ideals which can be said to be a factor of production. Thus, to govern to tackling poverty in all sphere in the short, medium and long term perspectives should be the country's charge. Each country is expected to design, execute, and monitor its poverty incidence profile and relate public policies and public expenditure towards targeting specific priorities and bring up, where possible, strict conditions against diversion from initial plan and accountability, transparency to governance built at times on pro-poor policies than always pro-growth policies.

The thesis that the process of distribution gives rise to no new value creates the tendency to attach little importance to distribution. Also, the thesis that machinery and other equipment produce no new value gives rise to a decisive lag in technological innovation. Ultimately, unless the Nigerian people accept a new philosophy and economics that replaces "capital," it will be difficult to fundamentally reconstruct its economy. This may not only be a truism in the Nigerian context, but the same can be said about all African nations and the developing countries as well.

The new philosophy may not be to destroy capital tendencies but rather to save the country from the mistaken ways of enslavement and master takes it all advocacies of our forefathers. Today's individual interest cannot transcend national interests. The leadership fears that the poor will struggle to have as much as they do or even higher given the opportunity should not be a factor but a total renaissance to making right the wrongs of the past. Thus, the thinking of: if assistance must be offered, it should only be passive assistance just for their survival than going beyond poverty line hence the so called social palliatives as N-power, etc. be uprooted from our thinking or reasoning. Even in socialist nations, the "nations of the discipline," the problem of dissipation may not be eliminated, but let the leading ideology for existence succeed in providing solution to the problem of the dissipation of human beings.

The African cum Nigerian problem has become a concern to the world hence the American President, Donald Trump statement on African leaders: "if 50 years of independence you have not built the necessary infrastructure for your people, are you humans? If you sit on gold, diamond, oil, manganese, uranium and your people don't have food, are you humans? If you stay in power and you buy weapons from strangers to kill your own citizens, are you humans? If your social protect is to stay in power for life, are you being human? If you leave your country health care unattended and treat yourself abroad, are you humans? Animals". Nigeria has to rise up to the task of improving the general economic well-being of the people and take

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up some challenging situation to charge and live above parochialism. Poverty, unemployment and ineptitude must be eradicated and it has to be the national focus. If that should be the only achievement of the leadership, it will be acknowledged as accomplished. The era of incessant looting of the common wealth and extreme individualism and abuse of power which had enthusiastically been the norm must be broken down hence the philosophy of statism give way to progressiveness and the worsening gap between the rich and the poor abridged. The creation of formidable middle class as a priority be the policy direction if the country is envisaging the path of sustainable economic and financial prosperity hence consistent efforts made towards tailoring the national budgets to empower small and medium scale businesses.

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